

ON THE KINETICS OF LONG CHAIN QUATERNARY SALT FORMATION*

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A new method has been developed to follow the kinetics of Menshutkin reaction by direct potentiometric titration of the disappearing base in non-aqueous medium. The method has been applied to study long chain quaternary salt formation. The reaction is found to be bimolecular running at a speed of the same order as that for lower halides under similar conditions. The solvent effect is also found to be similar to the previously found effect in the case of lower halides.

The rate of formation of quaternary salts by the reaction between an alkyl halide and a tertiary amine, which is some times called Menshutkin reaction, has been measured for a number of amines and halides under different conditions (Bell, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 36, 82; Richardson and Soper, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1873). However, there seems to be no study when either the amine or the halide is a long chain compound of soap-like length (C_{12} to C_{18}) and hence, the compound formed is a surface-active agent.

This may probably be ascribed to the fact that the hitherto used methods of following such reaction are inapplicable in this case. The long chain quaternary salts are fairly well soluble in non-polar solvents and hence it is not possible to apply the original precipitation and weighing method of Menshutkin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 6, 41). Neither it is possible to extract out ionisable halide with water and titrate it subsequently, as done by most later workers (cf. Pickels and Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1353; Edwards, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 1894) or extract out the excess base with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (Baker and Nathan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 519) because these surface-active agents form emulsion in presence of water.

This reaction, however, is of interest because many of these compounds, for example, cetyl pyridinium chloride, cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, octadecyl dimethylbenzylammonium chloride, etc., which are usually manufactured by such a reaction, have lately assumed great technical importance owing to their surface activity, germicidal power and other properties. We have undertaken a systematic study of the kinetics of this type of reaction and this communication is to make a preliminary report of our work.

EXPERIMENTAL

Our experimental method has been a direct and straightforward one and is different from that of all workers in this field. Since the reaction between, say, cetyl bromide and pyridine,

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involves a disappearance of the base, pyridine, with the progress of the reaction, the reaction has been followed by directly titrating the mixtures with acid after definite intervals. The difficulty of accurately titrating such weak base as pyridine, specially in presence of organic solvents, has been solved by taking help of the method recently developed by one of us (Palit, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 246; cf. Green, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1948, 37, 240; Siggia, "Quantitative Organic Analysis via Functional Groups", John Willy & Sons, pp. 21,69) for titrating very weak bases.

The reaction mixture (10 c.c.) which was $N/20$ with respect to both the base and the halide were sealed in pyrex glass ampules in vacuum by cooling in liquid air and evacuating. These ampules were heated in an oil thermostat maintained at constant temperature to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ for definite periods. The ampules were broken and the contents of each was dissolved in 20 c.c. of glycol-isopropyl mixtures and was titrated potentiometrically using glass electrode against decinormal perchloric acid in the same solvent.

The result of a typical run is shown in Fig. 1 and some data in Table I, where k_1 values are given without correction for expansion of the solvent medium. It will be observed from Fig. 1 that the reaction is easily followed by our technique and the data quoted in Table I show that the reaction is a bimolecular one proceeding smoothly

Fig. 1

Disappearance of pyridine (N/20) with progress of reaction with bromide (N/20) in methyl ethyl ketone as shown by potentiometric titration in glycol isopropyl alcohol medium.

up to well above 50% conversion without any appreciable change in the kinetics. These results further show that the solvent effect for these long chain reactions is essentially of the same type as shown by similar reactions with shorter chain compounds. This seems to indicate that the reaction mechanism is basically similar in both cases. Palit (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 752) has postulated a possible mechanism for the solvent effect of this type of reactions according to which this type of reactions is slowest in perfectly neutral solvents and is accelerated by the acidity (electron accepting power) or basicity of solvents, the acidity of solvents playing a stronger part. It was deduced that under identical conditions $k_{\text{CCl}_4} > k_{\text{CHCl}_3}$ and $k_{\text{benzene}} > k_{\text{cyclohexane}}$. Our results agree with the above expectation as also with the expected higher speed in alcohol owing to the comparatively high acidity of its hydroxylic hydrogen.

TABLE I

Bimolecular constant, k_2 (100°).

Solvent.	Reaction time.	% Reacted.	k_2 (mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ litre)	Mean k_2 .
Reaction: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{Br} + \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \rightarrow [\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NC}_5\text{H}_5]^+ \text{Br}^-$				
CCl_4	96 hrs.	7.78	0.000031	0.000032
	247	20.35	0.000034	
CHCl_3	29	28.05	0.00046	0.00041
	48	35.84	0.00040	
	100	52.72	0.00038	
$\text{CH}_3\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5$	6	9.26	0.00035	0.00052
	12	16.34	0.00053	
	54	45.12	0.00049	
$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$	12	34.34	0.00146	0.00147
	48	67.19	0.00147	
Reaction: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{Br} + \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \rightarrow [\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{NC}_5\text{H}_5]^+ \text{Br}^-$				
CCl_4	37	2.09	0.000020	0.000022
	158	9.42	0.000023	
	247	14.39	0.000023	
CHCl_3	29	23.7	0.00033	0.00032
	48	33.64	0.00033	
	100	49.52	0.00031	
$\text{CH}_3\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5$	6	8.75	0.00056	0.00054
	12	15.91	0.00055	
	54	43.76	0.00051	
$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$	12	31.12	0.00126	0.00127
	21	46.07	0.00136	
	48	63.48	0.00121	
Benzene	138	12.37	0.000030	0.000028
	264	19.30	0.000027	

Do (99.8°) $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{Br} + \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (pyridine) $\rightarrow [\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NC}_5\text{H}_5]^+ \text{Br}^-$ 2459×10^{-6}

Do (99.8°) $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{Br} + \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (pyridine) $\rightarrow [\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NC}_5\text{H}_5]^+ \text{Br}^-$ 10.1×10^{-6}

In the same table we have compared our data with a few similar data for lower alkyl bromides and pyridine. It will be observed that under identical conditions the

reaction studied by us proceeds with a speed of the same order as for the lower alkyl bromides. For example, in benzene our k_2 value for dodecyl bromide is 30×10^{-8} (corrected for expansion of solvent) against 24.9×10^{-8} for ethyl bromide as given by Pickels and Hinshelwood (*loc. cit.*). Quantitatively speaking, the longer chains run the reaction at a higher speed. Pickels and Hinshelwood observed the speed to decrease from 24.9×10^{-8} to 10.1×10^{-8} as they pass from ethyl to propyl bromide. We, however, find the speed to increase (except in methyl ethyl ketone) as we pass from dodecyl to hexadecyl bromide. It is possible that as we pass from methyl upwards the speed gradually drops and again begins to increase as we approach the soap-type length. It is difficult to discern from these preliminary results what part the inductive effect of the alkyl groups is playing in influencing the speed, but it seems, *a priori*, that this increase of speed is more likely due to a decrease in the heat of activation than to an increase in the PZ factor, because the entropy factor for such long chains will be unfavourable for reaction as oriented collisions will be necessary for the reaction. Work is in progress to thoroughly investigate the above points.

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